

ROLE OF CUSTOMS CONTROL IN DETECTING AND PREVENTING CRIMES COMMITTED AT INTERNATIONAL AIRPORTS.

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Abstract: Customs control plays an important role in ensuring the stable economic development of the country, in controlling the movement of foreign economic entities and residents and non-residents through border customs posts. Proposals regarding the development of visual surveillance mechanisms to increase the tourism attractiveness of our country and the effectiveness and improvement of the "Remote customs control" and "Customs without a customs officer" systems introduced at international airports in the detection and prevention of customs violations will be discussed.

Key words: border customs post, international standard, customs control forms, risk group, customs without a customs officer, declaration, visual surveillance, risk prevention, the dual-channel system, goods and material wealth.

Аннотация: Таможенный контроль играет важную роль в обеспечении устойчивого экономического развития страны, в контроле за перемещением субъектов внешнеэкономической деятельности, а также резидентов и нерезидентов через приграничные таможенные посты. Будут обсуждены предложения, касающиеся разработки механизмов визуального наблюдения для повышения туристической привлекательности нашей страны, а также эффективности и совершенствования систем "Удаленного таможенного контроля" и "контроля без участия сотрудника таможни", внедренных в международных аэропортах для выявления и предотвращения таможенных нарушений.

Ключевые слова: приграничный таможенный пост, международный стандарт, формы таможенного контроля, группа риска, таможня без сотрудника таможни, декларирование, визуальное наблюдение, предотвращение рисков, двухполосная система, товары и материальные ценности.

International airports serve as bustling gateways, facilitating the movement of millions of passengers and cargo across borders every day. While these hubs of connectivity are primarily designed for legitimate travel and trade, they also inadvertently attract individuals with illicit intentions. The evolving landscape of global crime, which includes drug trafficking, smuggling, money laundering, and terrorism, poses significant challenges to airport security and the integrity of international borders. In this complex environment, the role of customs control at international airports emerges as a critical and multifaceted aspect of national security.

According to the decree of October 11, 2017 No. 814 on the approval of the regulation on the procedure for the use of two-lane and remote customs control systems at transfer points through the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan, remote customs control was introduced at international airports. As a result, two-lane "green" and "red" control systems have been canceled in the departure terminals of Uzbekistan's international airports. They were replaced by remote customs control in accordance with international standards, which allows to reduce the time of crossing the border by three times. The remote customs control system allows inspectors to remotely monitor departures by means of surveillance cameras and analysis of flight information, excluding additional contacts and not restricting the movement of passengers. In addition, recommendations and guidelines made through the main website of the World Customs Organization are the legal basis of the article.

International customs control procedures at international airports are guided by several international standards and agreements to ensure consistency and facilitate

the smooth flow of international trade and travel. These standards are primarily established by organizations such as the World Customs Organization (WCO) and the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). Here are some of the key international standards and principles for customs control procedures at international airports:

WCO Framework of Standards to Secure and Facilitate Global Trade (SAFE Framework): The SAFE Framework, developed by the World Customs Organization, provides a set of international standards for customs procedures, including risk management, customs-to-customs cooperation, and the use of technology to enhance security while facilitating legitimate trade.

Customs Valuation: The World Trade Organization's Agreement on Customs Valuation provides guidelines for determining the customs value of imported goods, ensuring uniformity in customs valuation procedures.

Harmonized System (HS) Codes: The Harmonized System, developed and maintained by the World Customs Organization, is an international nomenclature for the classification of products. It ensures a consistent approach to classifying and identifying goods for customs purposes.

Customs Declarations: International standards require the submission of accurate and complete customs declarations by importers and exporters. These declarations should include information about the goods, their value, and other relevant details.

Customs Tariffs: Customs authorities worldwide maintain tariff schedules that provide the applicable duty rates for various goods. These schedules are often based on international agreements and provide transparency in customs duties.

Risk Management: Customs organizations use risk management principles to identify high-risk shipments and travelers. This approach allows customs authorities to allocate resources effectively and focus on potentially problematic transactions.

Customs-Trade Partnership Against Terrorism (C-TPAT): The C-TPAT program, initiated by U.S. Customs and Border Protection, is an example of a

voluntary partnership between customs authorities and businesses. It sets standards for supply chain security and trade compliance.

AEO (Authorized Economic Operator) Programs: Many countries have established AEO programs that provide certain benefits to businesses with a proven track record of compliance and security. These programs are based on WCO guidelines.

Cargo Screening: International standards require the screening of cargo shipments for security purposes. Technologies like X-ray scanners and sniffer dogs are used to detect contraband and other security threats.

Passenger Screening: ICAO sets international standards for passenger screening, including the use of biometric data, passport checks, and watchlist screening to enhance aviation security.

Information Sharing and Data Exchange: Customs organizations often participate in international data exchange systems to share information about cargo, passengers, and threats with other customs authorities and law enforcement agencies.

Mutual Recognition of Customs Procedures: Some countries engage in mutual recognition agreements to streamline customs procedures, such as the mutual recognition of AEO status, to expedite trade between trusted trading partners.

These international standards and agreements help promote consistency, transparency, and security in customs control procedures at international airports. They also facilitate the efficient flow of legitimate trade and travel while combating illicit activities and security threats. It's important for customs authorities and businesses involved in international trade to be aware of and comply with these standards to ensure smooth cross-border transactions.

Developing visual observation mechanisms to enhance the tourism attractiveness of your country can be a valuable initiative. To achieve this, you can study foreign experiences and adapt relevant strategies to your own context. Here are some steps to consider:

1. **Research and Benchmarking**
2. **Infrastructure Development**
3. **Sustainable Tourism**
4. **Marketing and Promotion**
5. **User Experience**
6. **Accessibility**
7. **Collaboration**
8. **Safety and Security**
9. **Community Engagement**
10. **Regulations and Permits**
11. **Feedback and Improvement**
12. **Sustainability and Conservation**

Improving the efficiency and effectiveness of "Remote Customs Control" and "Customs without a customs officer" systems involves leveraging technology, streamlining processes, and enhancing collaboration. These systems aim to expedite customs processes while maintaining security and compliance. Here are some proposals for enhancing these systems:

1. Implement Advanced Technology:

- Utilize modern technology, such as AI, machine learning, and blockchain, for automated document verification, risk assessment, and fraud detection. This can significantly reduce manual intervention.

2. Digitalization of Documents:

- Encourage the use of electronic documentation and e-signatures, reducing paperwork and speeding up the customs process.

3. Data Sharing and Integration:

- Enhance data sharing and integration between customs authorities, regulatory agencies, and stakeholders. Seamless data exchange improves decision-making and reduces duplication of efforts.

4. Mobile Applications:

- Develop mobile applications for travelers and shippers to submit information, declarations, and make payments. This streamlines the process and allows for pre-clearance.

5. Pre-Notification and Pre-Clearance:

- Allow shippers and travelers to submit information and documentation in advance, enabling customs authorities to pre-clear goods or people before they arrive at the border.

6. Trusted Trader Programs:

- Implement "Trusted Trader" programs that provide benefits to compliant businesses. This helps expedite their customs processes and reduces the burden on customs authorities.

7. Risk-Based Inspections:

- Use risk assessment models to focus resources on high-risk shipments or travelers, allowing low-risk items to clear customs more quickly.

8. Single Window Systems:

- Create single-window systems that enable businesses to submit all required information through a single platform. This simplifies the process and reduces redundancy.

9. Training and Capacity Building:

- Invest in training for customs officers and staff to ensure they are proficient in using advanced technology and are aware of the latest trade regulations.

10. Public Awareness and Education:

- Educate the public and businesses about the benefits of these systems to encourage participation and compliance.

11. Cybersecurity Measures:

- Implement robust cybersecurity measures to protect data and systems from cyber threats, ensuring the integrity of remote customs control and customs-less control systems.

12. Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:

- Regularly assess the performance of these systems, gather feedback, and make improvements based on the feedback and evolving technological advancements.

13. International Collaboration:

- Collaborate with neighboring countries and trading partners to create harmonized systems and mutually recognize each other's controls, simplifying cross-border trade.

14. Feedback Mechanisms:

- Establish feedback channels for users to report issues or provide input on how to improve the customs control systems. This helps in making iterative improvements.

15. Auditing and Accountability:

- Implement an auditing system to ensure that customs officers and related personnel are accountable for their actions and decisions.

By implementing these proposals, customs authorities can enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of remote customs control and customs-less control systems. These improvements can lead to faster clearance of goods and people, reduced costs for businesses, and more effective enforcement of customs regulations.

In conclusion, the customs control units at international airports are not just revenue collection agencies; they are the first line of defense against a myriad of criminal activities that threaten national security, public safety, and the integrity of international borders. Their vigilance and expertise in scrutinizing passengers, cargo, and luggage are paramount in ensuring that the facilitation of legitimate travel and trade does not inadvertently provide cover for illicit activities. The diverse range of crimes that customs officials combat, from drug trafficking and money laundering to smuggling and even terrorism, highlights the multifaceted and ever-evolving nature of their responsibilities. These professionals undergo rigorous training and stay abreast of the latest techniques and technologies to remain one step ahead of criminals. In an age where international connectivity continues to grow, the role of customs control becomes even more critical. The introduction of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, data analytics, and sophisticated scanning

equipment is enhancing their capabilities in identifying high-risk individuals and shipments. These tools empower customs officers to make more informed decisions and facilitate the expedited movement of legitimate travelers and goods.

In the end, the customs control function at international airports is a cornerstone of national security and global crime prevention. As these professionals work tirelessly to detect and prevent crimes committed at these transportation hubs, they stand as a formidable deterrent to those who would seek to exploit the pathways of international travel for illicit gain. Their contributions are essential in maintaining the safety and security of our interconnected world, ensuring that the benefits of global trade and mobility are not undermined by criminal activities.

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